

FEATURES OF DIALOGIC SPEECH

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ABSTRACT

When speaking a language, a person not only communicates information but also thinks and becomes aware of the hidden aspects of the natural world. Speech is the actual form of communication; language is merely a means of that. The language is not part of history, but the speech has historical characteristics. Language is a social phenomenon, while speaking is a mental phenomenon. The manner in which the speaker and the listener participate in communication are not necessarily the same. As a result, dialogic and monologic speech types develop. At the same time dialogic speech has several types. This paper presents information about dialogic speech.

Keywords: dialogic speech, language, work of art, communication, types of dialogic speech.

The scientific literature provides a definition of the word “communication.” For instance, the following is how the encyclopedia defines it:

1) connection, a mode of; connection of one place with another; and 2) contact, or the transmission of information from one person to another, is a cognitive activity. Communication is language's primary function. When talking, a person not only uses words to transmit information but also analyzes and perceives the hidden aspects of the natural world around them. This is the function of language in communication. This crucial task establishes the language's existence. The importance of the communication task is such that it affects how languages arise and develop. Conversations take up 70% of a person's time, according to researchers “Speech is the behavior of a person who utilizes language to interact with other group members. Conversation is the use of several linguistic forms to convey complicated content, including requests or pleas as well as information.” Language is necessary for the clarity and effectiveness of speech, and speech is necessary for the existence of language. Speech both creates and manifests language. Speech is communication in and of itself if language is a tool for it. Despite being closely related and connected, language and speech have characteristics that set them apart from one another. Thus, language is a means of communication. Speech is the process of communication. Speech is individual. It is the speech acts, habits, speech, and writing of separate people. It is impossible to observe language as a means of communication. Speech is historical, but language is beyond

history. Speech depends on the circumstances in which it is used. Speech is dynamic compared to language. Speech is an individual and mental phenomenon, but language is a social phenomenon. Speech is a creative activity and a habit of an individual. Speech and language are different in terms of structure as well. The structure of the language shows itself in its largest unit, the sentence. The structure of speech includes sentences, paragraphs, and text. Although the differences exist, speech and language are interrelated. "Language is essential for speech to be clear and to show its full effect; speech, in turn, is essential for the establishment of language; historically, the presence of speech always precedes language." The participation of the speaker and the listener in the speech process is not always the same. The speaker and the listener almost act equally in the speech process: the speaker asks, and the listener responds; the speaker expresses his/her opinion; the interlocutor expresses his/her attitude. In another form of speech, the listener does not interfere with the conversation of the interlocutor due to a need or opportunity. Such interpretation and listening create monologic and dialogic forms of speech.

Dialogical speech. This is a type of speech where two or more people communicate. If during a monological speech a person speaks and the others listen, dialogic speech takes place between the participants of the conversation. It is worth noting that the elements of dialogic speech are reflected in monological speech and vice versa. The remarkable feature of dialogical speech is that the topic of such speech is very specific and concise. The speech is often accompanied by sentence substitutes such as "Yes!" or "No!". Incomplete sentences, intonation, facial expressions, and gestures are widely used in dialogic speech. Dialogical speech is popular in fiction. In dramatic works, dialogue serves to advance the plot and reveal the characteristics of the characters. Dialogue can be short or long, depending mainly on the content of the speech.

Dialogic speech has types such as question-and answer, interview, discussion, etc. During the dialogue, lexical repetitions, responding to questions with questions, word order violations in sentences, elliptical construction of thoughts, pauses, etc. are acceptable. Certainly, expect normal intonation to be followed to ensure understanding in such a communication process, along with observing all the norms of the language. Dialogic speech is also referred to as dialogue. It is a brief and abbreviated form of speech, characteristic of spoken language. The phrases are slightly short, and the syntactic structures are simple. Incomplete sentences are frequently used. Gestures, facial expressions, hand movements, etc. are extensively used in this type of speech. Intonation plays a significant role in dialogic speech. Dialogue can be micro-dialogue or macro-dialogue. A micro-dialogue consists of short dialogues between several people. Examples of micro-dialogue can be found in fiction-examples of epic oral literature: fables, fairy tales, legends, anecdotes, and epics, as well as memoirs, essays,

stories, novellas, narratives, and novels. Macro-dialogue covers the structure of works of art. Dramatic works are created based on macro-dialogue. Dialogical speech has five forms of dialogue: 1) monologic dialogue; 2) conversation or conversational dialogue 3) question-and-answer dialogue; 4) interview dialogue; 5) discussion dialogue. The participants of the monologic dialogue describe the event, person, or matter in detail; express their negative or positive attitude toward them; and convey the person, thing, or event they are discussing to their interlocutor and listeners using various proofs and evidence. The frequent change of intonation in a conversational dialogue increases the emotionality and impact of the speech without additional words as an artistic tool. In the question-and-answer dialogue of dialogic speech, the main terms for the speaker are to have a rich vocabulary and to perfectly master the rules of our language to convey the idea to the listener clearly.

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